

1 **This preprint have not been certified by peer review**

2 **The green side of social innovation: using Sustainable Development Goals to classify environmental**
3 **impacts of rural grassroots initiatives**

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11 **Abstract**

12 Social Innovations are grassroots processes aiming to achieve impacts beyond an individual level and
13 towards a broader societal good. The environmental dimension of impacts refers to any direct change
14 to the environment resulting from social innovation activities, products, or services, which are not
15 addressed by pre-existing systems. In this paper, we determine the role of social innovation in
16 addressing environmental impacts by analysing a database of social innovation examples in European
17 and circum-Mediterranean rural areas, compiled within the H2020 Project SIMRA. We conceptualise
18 the overall aim of environmentally-focused social innovation initiatives as furthering the sustainable
19 development of their territories. To address the environmental impacts of initiatives in a structured
20 way, we use the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) classification, to describe social innovation
21 environmental impacts in relation to specific targets. We analysed 238 initiatives from the SIMRA
22 catalogue and associated initiative websites to identify and classify their direct environmental impacts.
23 Our results indicate that 68% of the cases have at least one direct environmental impact that aligns
24 with a SDG target. The most common impacts are related to sustainable natural resource management
25 (SDGs target 12.2), sustainable food production systems (2.4), and equal access to land (2.3). This SDG-
26 based classification proved to be a useful analytical tool for categorizing internationally policy-relevant
27 environmental impacts of social innovations.

28 **Keywords**

29 Agriculture, Bottom-up approaches, Ecological transition, Forestry, Rural development, Sustainable
30 resource management

31 **1. Introduction and Literature review**

32 **1.1. Introduction**

33 The impact of human behaviour on the environment has surged at the planetary scale over the past
34 half century. Natural cycles have been drastically disrupted by overpopulation, pollution, fossil fuels
35 consumption, land use changes, and deforestation, among other causes (Steffen et al., 2018). Such
36 changes have triggered cascading effects on global weather patterns and ecosystems including climate
37 change, biodiversity loss, soil and land degradation, and pollution of water and air (NASA, 2020;
38 Cardinale et al., 2012). Moreover, impacts from climate change and environmental degradation extend
39 well beyond direct planetary ecosystems shifts, having detrimental effects on human health, food
40 supply, energy and renewable resources stocks, and societal stability.

41 If humanity wishes to stop exceeding planetary boundaries, major transformations are needed in the
42 way we interact with our surrounding environment. Several programmes and strategies have been
43 developed at international levels to reverse the environmental impacts of climate change and to
44 transform current societal and economic patterns. These include (i) binding international agreements
45 to stimulate alternative human consumption models such as The Paris Agreement (United Nations,
46 2015), EU Bioeconomy Strategy (European Commission, 2018), and the Recast of the Renewable
47 Energies Directive (European Parliament, 2016), and (ii) internationally agreed indicator frameworks
48 paving the way for a new blueprint for human society. The latter includes the eight Millennium
49 Development Goals (United Nations, 2013) and the follow-up programme of the seventeen Sustainable
50 Development Goals (SDG) (United Nations, 2015b), which addresses the global environmental,
51 economic, and social challenges humanity faces, in a holistic way. The SDGs are designed as social
52 contracts “*between the world's leaders and the people*” for a new “*shared vision of humanity*” (UN
53 News, 2015). They aim at activating and supporting global, national, and local, initiatives and
54 programmes which focus on achieving one or several goals by 2030.

55 While regulatory and restrictive approaches are important policy instruments to halt human-induced
56 environmental degradation and rebalance human-nature interactions, they might fail to deliver their
57 expected objectives due to *inter alia* political resistance and/or the need for large up-front investments
58 towards control and patrolling (e.g. field officers). Additionally, they have been criticized due to their
59 inability to mediate “the dynamic behaviour of social- ecological systems” (Olsson and Galaz, 2012). All
60 over the world, groups of people, communities, and citizens have recognised the need for cooperation,
61 coordination, and alliances to tackle both global and local environmental challenges.

62 The discrepancy between governance systems at local and global levels has been addressed by both
63 ecological resilience and social-ecological literature (MacKinnon and Derickson, 2013, Folke et al.,
64 2007), which indicates the need to create new governance system which function at multiple scales
65 (global to local) and spheres (biophysical to human well-being; Olsson and Galaz, 2012). In this sense,
66 environmental social innovations play an important role in complementing the limitation of top-down
67 normative frameworks (Green et al., 2014). New collective strategies and networks create discussion
68 platforms where shared decisions are taken to change paradigms and for (progressively) achieving
69 societal transformations and ecological transitions towards a common wellbeing (e.g., Slow Food, a
70 global and grassroots organization, created in 1989 to preserve food cultures and traditional farming
71 production models). These governance models are defined in the literature as Social Innovations (SI), as
72 they imply new collaborative interactions involving community members, private actors, and public
73 bodies (Polman et al., 2017; Moulaert et al., 2013; Neumeier, 2012). SI is a scientific construct
74 generating important academic debates (e.g. see in Edwards-Schachter and Wallace, 2017; Pol and
75 Ville, 2009). It is also of increasing relevance in the policy environment, thanks to its inherent flexibility
76 and breadth. SI encapsulates a wide variety of examples (e.g., from agriculture to forestry, from urban
77 to rural networks, from associations to public-private partnerships), all aiming at tackling community
78 problems through changed social and economic behaviours. While studies in the literature have
79 identified how social and environmental impacts in SI are tightly interlinked (Baker & Mehmood, 2015),
80 to the best of our knowledge no studies have performed a systematized review of environmental
81 impacts of SI initiatives.

82 To fill this gap, this study determines the role of SI in addressing environmental impacts. We focus our
83 analysis on a selection of local and international SI initiatives in European and circum-Mediterranean
84 rural areas, compiled by the EU Horizon 2020 project, Social Innovation in Marginalized Rural Areas
85 (SIMRA). The SIMRA project provided an advanced understanding of the mechanisms behind SI
86 development in marginalized rural areas, in the fields of agriculture, forestry and rural development
87 (Zenodo, 2019). Project outcomes include: a definition of SI tailored to marginalised rural areas

88 (Polman et al; 2017), a detailed set of tools to evaluate SI and its impacts (Secco et al., 2020; Kluvankova
89 et al., 2021), One of the largest available database of SI examples (Valero & Bryce, 2020).

90 Studying environmental impacts of SI in rural communities is particularly relevant as rural societies are
91 often strongly connected with their surrounding environment. Thus, we expect to identify a large share
92 of rural SI initiatives operate based on human-environment interactions. To assess environmental
93 impacts of SI in a structured way, we use the SDG classification, which permits the description of SI
94 environmental impacts through a series of disaggregated policy targets. Our specific research questions
95 are: (a) what are the environmental impacts of rural SI initiatives? and (b) to what extent does SI
96 contribute to a green transition? To address these questions, we explore in which fields different SI
97 initiatives are aligned with environmental policy objectives and therefore support SDGs environmental
98 targets.

99 1.2. Literature review

100 Social Innovation

101 In this study, we conceptualize Social Innovation (SI) following the definition developed by Polman et
102 al. (2017), stating that SI is a “*reconfiguration of social practices in response to societal challenges, which*
103 *seeks to enhance outcomes on societal well-being and necessarily includes the engagement of civil*
104 *society actors*”. Although we acknowledge that many alternative SI definitions exist (e.g. Edwards-
105 Schachter et al., 2017; Moulaert et al., 2013; Neumeier, 2012; Pol et al., 2009), we follow Polman et al
106 (2017)’s definition for three main reasons. First, it stresses the centrality of human agency in SI
107 processes, as the requisite catalyst to initiate changes in attitudes, behaviours, and governance. Agency
108 is regarded as the “*ability to recognise needs, exploit contextual social, normative and financial*
109 *resources and to engage civil society through collective actions*” (Dalla Torre et al., 2020). Through
110 collective actions, agency engages people in SI processes promoting new ecological, social, or
111 institutional practices (Folke et al., 2010). At the local level, this differs from the transformative power
112 of social innovation, proposed by Haxeltine et al (2017). Transformative SI indicates the ability of SI
113 processes to “alter and/or replace dominant institutions”. In the rural context, the transformative
114 power of SI models is often limited, and tend to coexist with institutionalised and traditional schemes
115 (e.g. environmental friendly tourism initiatives vis-a-vis traditional tourism models). Nonetheless there
116 exist some cases of transformative SI models in rural areas active at both local and global levels (e.g.
117 Slow Food; Avelino et al., 2019). The opportunity for socio-ecological systems to be transformed in
118 ways that favour sustainable outcomes depends to an extent on their adaptive capacity as described
119 by Folke et al. (2000). Such capacity is underpinned by a ‘learning by doing’ approach which can be
120 implemented where social networks are flexible and can reconfigure in response to challenges and new
121 information.

122 Second, Polman et al. (2017) distinguish between processes, products, and outcomes/impacts and
123 consider the reconfiguring of social practices to be the central process of SI (the initiating process by
124 the innovators and early followers after a triggering event) while the emerging new networks,
125 governance arrangements or attitudes as the products. Enhanced social, economic, or environmental
126 wellbeing can be considered the impacts and outcomes of the SI (Secco et al., 2017). This tripartite
127 subdivision of the contribution of SI to human lives is useful for the purpose of our study as it allows us
128 to define and isolate the environmental-impact dimension of SI.

129 Third, this definition emphasizes the role of SI in transforming unmet needs of society into future
130 opportunities for enhanced societal wellbeing. This is a relevant viewpoint as it characterises SI as a
131 phenomenon that emerges as a response to key necessities/opportunities not yet exploited (Neumeier,
132 2017). Shocks (e.g. earthquakes, floods, wildfires) and the consequences of climate change can thus be
133 considered in many cases as the triggering factors of pro-environmental SI actions due to unmet socio-

134 ecological needs (e.g. lack of security and normalcy due to wildfires occurrence; Górriz-Mifsud et al.,
135 2019). Not all SIs start as bottom-up initiatives as they can also filter down from higher level schemes
136 or can be a combination of both bottom-up and top-down approaches. Good examples of multi-level
137 initiatives are for instance the “Covenant of mayors” (2021) where communities are supported by the
138 European Union to find local solutions to current climate change issues, and the LEADER programme
139 (ENRD, 2016) where the European Union supports rural development projects initiated at the local level
140 to revitalize rural areas and create jobs.

141

142 Finally, in this paper we focus our analysis on European and circum-Mediterranean rural areas. SI is a
143 phenomenon which has been relatively well studied in the urban environment (e.g. Moulaert et al.,
144 2010), but not in rural areas. This is a relevant research gap especially for the environmental governance
145 sphere, as often rural areas are places where the environment holds strongly in people imaginaries
146 (Hinds & Sparks, 2008), and thus where environmental crisis and shocks can act as powerful triggers
147 for the emergence of SI towards the establishment of new sustainable development models.

148

149 **Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)**

150 The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development was adopted at the United Nations Sustainable
151 Development Summit on 25 September 2015 and includes the 17 Sustainable Development Goals
152 (SDGs) and 169 related targets, which recommend action on various social and environmental issues
153 (United Nations, 2015b). The Agenda applies to all countries and is now the major framework for
154 guiding development policies and efforts across local to global scales (Katila et al., 2019). SDGs
155 recognize that ending poverty and other deprivations must go hand in hand with strategies that
156 improve health and education, reduce inequality, enhance economic growth through affordable and
157 clean energy, promote innovation and enhance infrastructure, promote responsible consumption and
158 production, while at the same time tackle climate change and preserve the ecological condition of
159 aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems. SI is thus considered a key component in fulfilling the SDGs
160 milestones by 2030 (Ravazzoli and Valero, 2020; Millard, 2018).

161 Many international governance mechanisms (e.g. the European Union Bioeconomy Strategy) are
162 aligned with the SDGs (Ludvig et al., 2019). It is thus logical to use them for operationalising the analysis
163 of the environmental impacts of SI initiatives, especially when the extent to which SI contributes to
164 environmental-related outcomes is a rather unexplored field. Several studies have used the SDGs
165 framework for assessing the positive role of SI in addressing socio-economic challenges. Eichler and
166 Schwarz (2019) carried out a review on which SDGs are addressed by SI initiatives. They showed that
167 most of their examined SI case studies dealt with an improvement of human health and well-being.
168 Flinzberger et al. (2020) carried out a Delphi study focused on which SDGs can be considered relevant
169 for agroforestry systems, and how to translate them into suitable indicators for labelling agroforestry
170 products. Katila et al. (2020) studied how the different aspects of land tenure rights are included and
171 addressed by the SDGs and their specific targets. Secure rights to land and resources are a prerequisite
172 for sustainable use of land and natural resources and are therefore essential for sustainable
173 development.

174 These earlier results show that SI initiatives can have impacts (direct or indirect) on specific SDGs
175 targets. Given the large number of SDGs and related targets, both synergic interactions and trade-offs
176 are inevitable. Kroll et al. (2019) found notable synergies across certain goals (e.g. SDG 13 Climate
177 Action with SDG 11 and 6), and trade-offs for other goals, including a serious nonalignment between
178 clean energy provision and poverty reduction. In contrast, the results from Hegre et al. (2020) based
179 on global data 2000–2016 indicate that synergies between and within SDGs prevail. Scherer et al.
180 (2018) observed that pursuing social goals is, generally, associated with higher environmental impacts.
181 Entities developing SDGs-based strategies should thus acknowledge interactions across Goals, and their

182 actions need to be designed reflecting upon the type and directionality of the interaction, its strength
183 and certainty, and different context-based factors to assess whether certain degree of trade-offs are
184 acceptable (Nilsson et al., 2016). SI would inherently aim at (at least) maintaining or improving socio-
185 economic conditions -in addition- to leverage environmental problems, thus intuitively making the
186 chances for trade-offs more unlikely. However, these trade-offs are not completely inexistent as social
187 innovators (unless they are public entities) are generally driven by effectiveness, sustainability, and
188 viability principles rather than policy coherence. Although acknowledging the existence of both trade-
189 offs and synergies across SDGs, the focus of this paper is to identify whether SI, besides delivering
190 intrinsic socio-economic impacts, also fulfil a series of environmental impacts framed using the SDG
191 nomenclature.

192 Finally, studying the role of SI models in delivering positive environmental impacts is also relevant in
193 the field of ecosystem management. Rather than being static systems, ecosystems are constantly
194 evolving and changing (Santamaría & Méndez, 2012). Modern ecosystem management theories have
195 shifted their focus from attempting to maintain ecosystems in some fixed optimal state to guiding
196 ecological change along desirable trajectories. Several published examples point to the key role that
197 local collaborative and adaptive approaches play in comparison to sectoral expert-centred approaches
198 in the field of ecosystem management (Biggs et al., 2010). Assessing the environmental impacts of SIs,
199 can thus provide valuable insights on understanding the conditions and processes necessary to
200 stimulate institutional transformation in ecosystem management in other areas and at larger scales.

201 **2. Materials and methods**

202 **2.1. SI initiatives catalogue**

203 The SI initiatives analysed in this study were drawn from a catalogue of both local and international SI
204 examples in the fields of forestry, agriculture and rural development covering Europe and countries
205 south and east of the Mediterranean. The examples were collected from a range of sources including
206 academic literature and in consultation with academics and stakeholders and together form a key
207 output of the SIMRA project: Catalogue of Diversity of Social Innovation (Valero & Bryce, 2020). The
208 catalogue categorises SI based on a range of variables including the challenges addressed, sector, topic,
209 institutional form, key partners, social practices and resulting social change alongside geographical
210 information. It contains over 400 initiatives of which 238 are validated SI examples according to the
211 definition developed by SIMRA (Polman et al., 2017), and 23 were analyzed in the project as in-depth
212 empirical case studies (agriculture: Baselice et al., 2021; forestry: Barlagne et al., 2021; Rural
213 Development Perlik, 2021; Fisheries: Vassilopoulos et al., 2021). We used the 238 validated SI
214 initiatives as our dataset. The examples cover a rich diversity of SI: prominent topics of focus include
215 social farming, provision of public services, valorisation of traditional land management practices,
216 entrepreneurship, and initiatives to support vulnerable groups. The catalogue consists of descriptive
217 narratives of the SI cases. These describe the objectives and outcomes of initiatives, where these are
218 known, and refer to social, economic, cultural, and environmental impacts. We used these descriptive
219 narratives to ascertain whether SI initiatives had resulted in environmental impact and the nature of
220 these impacts.

221 **2.2. Data collection and data processing**

222 To classify the environmental impacts of selected SI initiatives through the SDGs framework, we used a
223 tripartite methodology. Firstly, we identified what can be considered as an “environmental impact” in
224 the frame of our study. Secondly, we identified which of the 169 SDGs targets contain a clear
225 environmental component, according to step 1. Finally, we performed an expert evaluation of the case

226 study catalogue (2.1) with the aim of identifying their potential contribution to SDG environmental
227 targets.

228 From an environmental viewpoint, we can categorise impacts of SI initiatives as: (i) those that target
229 socio-economic needs (decent jobs, livelihood strategies) and/or cultural aspects (heritage
230 preservation); (ii) those that explicitly target environmental improvements. In the first category, the
231 primary focus of SI initiatives is on socio-economic aspects, but given they are based on sustainable use
232 of natural resources (e.g. green transport systems for improving local economic development), they
233 are associated with environmental-friendly practices (e.g. recycling). In the second category,
234 environmental impacts are the primary focus of the SI and thus easier to identify.

235 To ascertain the environmental impacts of SI initiatives, we use the following definition of impact: *‘the*
236 *changes which are expected to happen due to the implementation and application of a given SI initiative’*
237 (Secco et al., 2017). As follows, such changes might result in environmental, social, economic, or
238 institutional impacts (Ravazzoli et al., 2021). From a socio-ecological perspective, our focus on
239 environmental impacts refers to any change in the ecological subsystem related to the societal
240 challenges addressed by the SI's activities, products, or services (e.g. Secco et al. 2017). While impacts
241 can be both direct and indirect, we identified direct changes only, as they are clearly related to the SI
242 activities and thus more accurately identifiable from available secondary data. Amongst such direct
243 impacts we considered those that are generated by purposeful actions which are intended or foreseen
244 by the actors of the SI initiative, and not those that are unintended. Fig.1 provides a graphic hierarchical
245 scheme showing the working definition of impact in use in this study. In orange, we indicate the impacts
246 considered.

247 Ravazzoli et al. (2019) identified the following environmental impacts of SI through empirical research:
248 (i) reduced vulnerability to environmental risks (ii) enhanced wellbeing and human health, (iii) reduced
249 ecological degradation of environmental assets, and (iv) enhanced socio-economic value through the
250 preservation and promotion of environmental assets. Given this assessment referred to a limited set of
251 case studies, the current study uses a more objective protocol to categorize environmental impacts of
252 SI: the SDGs framework. Our application differs to that used by Eichler and Schwarz (2019), where they
253 looked at the relationship between SI and all SDGs. We focus only on goals strictly related to the
254 environment, and their relative sub-targets. Although the 2030 SDGs Agenda includes 17 goals and 169
255 targets with a total of 247 indicators (United Nations, 2015b), we stay at the target level owing to the
256 difficulties in compiling disaggregated environmental data at the administrative level in which most of
257 our analysis falls. Almost half of the SDG targets require environmental statistics to be able to compile
258 its indicators and enable regular monitoring of progress¹.

259 We reviewed all 169 SDGs targets, as they are presented in the *Global indicator framework for the*
260 *Sustainable Development Goals and targets of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development* (United
261 Nations, 2020). The Environment Statistics Section of the United Nations (United Nations, 2016)
262 categorizes the 17 SDGs into three groups: (a) those having a full environmental dimension (Goals 6, 7,
263 11, 12, 13, 14 and 15), (b) SDGs partially integrating the environment in some of their targets (Goals 2,
264 3, 8, 9), and (c) SDGs without a clear environmental component (Goals 1, 4, 5, 10, 16, 17). To validate
265 this broad categorization, we closely scrutinized each SDGs target definition to determine whether the
266 scope of the target included any direct environmental impact. Following this additional assessment,

¹ The existing Framework for the Development of Environment Statistics (FDES), its Basic Set of Environment Statistics (BSES), and the Environment Statistics Self-Assessment Tool (ESSAT) (United Nations, 2016) are the most widely used tools for developing environment statistics at national level. However, such tools have been disregarded as the macro-statistics that they provide cannot support in assessing the environmental-related impacts of SI initiatives with local/regional level.

267 we selected a final list of 65 SDGs targets with an environmental dimension. This further classification
268 excluded certain targets from group (a) (6.2, 6.a, 7.b, 11.1, 11.c, 12.1, 12.a), while including additional
269 targets from group (c) (1.4, 1.5 and 17.14). Appendix 1 lists the 65 selected targets identified in this
270 study having a direct impact on the environment. These targets were used to classify the 238 SI
271 initiatives of the catalogue.

272 To identify the environmental impacts of the 238 SI initiatives, we performed an expert evaluation
273 assessment based on the existing information available in the SIMRA catalogue. We firstly identified
274 whether each of the SI initiatives had any direct and intended environmental impacts through its
275 activities. If so, we classified the SI environmental impact using a matrix of the 65 SDGs related targets.
276 When the targets included several impact fields (e.g. the 1.4 SDG target, focusing on equal access to
277 natural resources, but also on microfinance and gender equality aspects), we made sure that we
278 assessed the SI case exclusively on the environment dimension. When the SI initiative description did
279 not offer sufficient information in the database, or in the external references provided (scientific
280 publications, grey literature, SI initiative website) to be properly assessed, the SI initiative was excluded
281 from the analysis (11 excluded). Similarly, when the SI initiative was assessed as not addressing any
282 environmental target, it was also excluded from the analysis (57 excluded).

283 2.3. Data analysis

284 To identify patterns across SI initiatives in relation to their environmental impacts, we performed a
285 mixed qualitative and quantitative analysis. To tackle our first research question, we ran a series of
286 descriptive univariate statistical analyses on the dataset. Firstly, we computed the total number of SI
287 initiatives covering at least one environmental SDG target, as well as the frequency of SDGs by cases.
288 These descriptive analyses allowed us to identify which share of the sample has positive impacts on the
289 environmental sphere, as well as to identify which are the most common environmental SDGs across
290 our sample. In the second analysis, we assessed the cases by a series of descriptors (e.g. scale, sector,
291 year of establishment), which allowed us to identify any relevant intra-case pattern. For our second
292 research question, we used a dendrogram as a diagrammatic representation to identify groupings of
293 CS based on similar environmental SDGs patterns (Appendix 2). The dendrogram was produced using
294 Ward's method as clustering criterion (Ward, 1963). By inspecting the dendrogram, we were able to
295 identify 9 grouping levels, which were further qualitatively classified by means of their most abundant
296 environmental SDG targets. The dendrogram also allowed us to assess the consistency of such
297 quantitative automatic classification. Through that, we were able to further identify nine initiatives
298 which were wrongly assessed and thus removed from the sample, bringing the final dataset to 161
299 observations. All quantitative analyses were performed in Excel and using the computing environment
300 R (R Core Team, 2020).

301 3 Results

302 3.1. Descriptive statistics

303 Of the 238 SI initiatives assessed, 68% appear to have one or more impacts of their activities linked to
304 the environment, while the remaining ones impact on other spheres (e.g. social inclusion of vulnerable
305 groups, elderly care, art and culture preservation, etc.). Within the environmental sub-sample, the
306 most common impacts are related to sustainable natural resource management (SDGs target 12.2; 47%
307 of the SI initiatives with environmental impacts), sustainable food production systems (SDGs target 2.4;
308 43%), equal access to land (SDGs target 2.3; 40%), policy coherence for sustainable development (SDGs
309 target 17.14; 31%), conservation restoration and sustainable use of Earth's ecosystems (SDGs target
310 15.1; 29%), protecting and safeguarding the world's natural heritage (SDGs target 11.4; 27%),
311 sustainable forest management (SDGs target 15.2; 25%), and increasing environmental awareness

312 (SDGs target 12.8; 24%) (Fig.2). Eleven SDGs targets were judged as having an environmental-oriented
313 focus but were not present in the SI initiatives catalogue. These include targets related to drinking water
314 (6.1), fossil-fuel subsidies rationalization (12.c), climate change awareness (13.a), marine preservation
315 (14.3, 14.4, 14.5, 14.6, 14.7, 14.a, 14.c), and combating species poaching and trafficking (15.c). Most of
316 the SI environmental initiatives in the dataset contribute to 2-3 SDG targets (35% of the overall cases;
317 Fig.3). A smaller number of initiatives (9%) contribute to a large spectrum of SDG targets (more than
318 10 targets).

319 Table 1 displays the SI initiatives categorized by number of SDG targets they address and their relative
320 geographical scale, sector, and establishment date. This result shows that most of the SI initiatives of
321 the study sample are local and established within the past ten years. This is an expected pattern, which
322 reflects the initial composition of the sample. Interestingly, initiatives that address up to five SDG
323 targets are mainly representative of the rural development sector (39%), followed by agricultural and
324 forestry cases (17% and 11% respectively). A small share of forestry and rural development SIs cover
325 multiple SDG targets (3% impacting 11-15 SDG targets, and 1% impacting 16-18 targets for both
326 sectors), with agriculture not being so multidimensional.

327 3.2. Classification of SI initiatives into groups

328 The tree diagram classifying the SI initiatives into groups of similar environmental SDG targets,
329 identified nine groups of SI initiatives with different environmental governance focus (Fig.4):

- 330 1. Group 1: **Increasing awareness for environmental protection.** This group includes 12 SI
331 initiatives (7.5% of the total) addressing mostly SDG target 12.8, and less frequently 11.4 and
332 13.3.
- 333 2. Group 2: **Sustainable tourism for natural protection and coherent policy development.** This
334 group has 12 initiatives (7.5%) covering 3.5 SDG targets in average and mainly 8.9, 11.4, and
335 less frequently 17.14.
- 336 3. Group 3: **Sustainable and renewable energy.** With 12 initiatives (7.5%), an average of 3.9 SDGs
337 targets per case and having as most frequent 7.1, 7.2, 7.3, and 17.14.
- 338 4. Group 4: **Sustainable food production models in agriculture.** This group has 16 initiatives (10%)
339 1.6 SDG targets in average covering mainly 2.3 and 2.4.
- 340 5. Group 5: **Waste reduction and recycling.** This group includes 8 initiatives (5%) addressing
341 mainly the SDG targets 12.5. This group has an average of 1.8 targets per case.
- 342 6. Group 6: **Hubs and partnerships to improve sustainable territorial development.** This group (15
343 initiatives; 9%) focuses on SDG targets 1.4, 17.14, and less frequently 2.3. This group has an
344 average of 2.3 targets per case.
- 345 7. Group 7: **Sustainable agriculture for a better management of natural resources and heritage,**
346 with 33 initiatives (20.5%), an average of 4.9 targets per case, focusing on targets 2.3, 2.4, 12.2,
347 and less frequently 11.4.
- 348 8. Group 8: **Sustainable forest management.** This group includes 19 initiatives (12%) addressing
349 SDG targets 12.2, 15.2, and less frequently 15.1. It has an average of 3.8 targets per case.
- 350 9. Group 9 **Multi-targets initiatives.** This group includes 34 SI initiatives (21%), which cover
351 multiple SDG targets, with an average of 12.7 targets per case.

352 Details of each group are presented in the next subsections and in Appendix 3.

353 3.2.1 Increasing awareness for environmental protection

354 The SI initiatives of this group share a strong environmental awareness component focused on: (i)
355 awareness raising activities for sustainable development (SDG 13 - climate action; SDG 12 -responsible
356 consumption and production); (ii) improving awareness of natural and cultural landscape heritage

357 preservation (SDG 11 - sustainable cities and communities). Their overall aim is to reconcile society with
358 nature through educational experiences, which can foster sustainable and traditional practices.

365 **3.2.2 Sustainable tourism for natural protection and coherent policy development**

360 This group includes 12 initiatives, which focus primarily on two environmental axes: (i) promotion of
361 sustainable touristic practices (SDG 8 - Decent work and economic growth), (ii) strengthened efforts to
362 safeguard natural heritage (SDG 11 – Sustainable cities and communities). Their scope includes the
363 promotion of alternative touristic habits and/or destinations harmonized with local natural capital,
364 which can support local communities’ development and preservation of local traditions.

365 **3.2.3 Sustainable and renewable energy**

366 Twelve energy related initiatives are included in this group, focusing on either supply of energy through
367 direct installations or through mechanisms allowing access to renewable energy, like cooperatives, land
368 ownership, third sector local development agencies. All energy sources were renewable (SDG 7 –
369 Affordable and clean energy) and nature-based with installations based on the following sources: (i)
370 water/hydroelectric, (ii) forest biomass, (iii) wind, and (iv) mixed renewable sources. Policy adherence
371 mechanisms or network development were only evident in a minority of cases (SDG target 17.14), and
372 in one case the SI initiated to replace a policy failure. Sustainable use of resources (SDG 11) were linked
373 to landscape approaches that included cultural heritage (SDG target 12.2).

374 **3.2.4 Sustainable food production models in agriculture**

375 The SI initiatives in this group aim at achieving sustainable food production models in agriculture. Most
376 of the SI are social farming and farming cooperatives tackling the social and economic aspects of
377 organising supply chains and enhancing human well-being. Reducing poverty and preventing social
378 exclusion are important transversal and non-environmental themes in this group. The SI cases in group
379 4 are most frequently addressing environmental targets related to SDG target 2.3 (double the
380 agricultural productivity and incomes of small-scale food producers), and SDG target 2.4 (ensure
381 sustainable food production systems and implement resilient agricultural practices). Group 4 has much
382 in common with group 7 as most of the cases involve local, organic and/or traditional agricultural
383 products and aim to maintain attractive rural areas. However, the focus of group 4 is on social and well-
384 being outcomes (poverty reduction and social inclusion) along with sustainable food production
385 models, while group 7 has a more specific focus on conservation agriculture, sustainable land use, and
386 sustainable use of natural resources.

387 **3.2.5 Waste reduction and recycling**

388 This group includes 13 initiatives focusing on sustainable development practices through waste
389 reduction, recycling, and increased efficiency. Most contribute to SDG 12.5 – substantially reduce waste
390 generation through prevention, reduction, recycling, and reuse.

391 **3.2.6 Hubs and partnerships to improve territorial development**

392 This group compiles very heterogeneous initiatives, which range from local co-ops and social farms, to
393 landscape and national-level approaches. These initiatives contain a relevant coordination component
394 as they are either networks or umbrella platforms or represent a coalition between different agents.
395 These SIs reflect alliances between actors of different sectors with a wider rural developmental vision
396 than in the other groups (more sectorial-specific), contributing mainly to the SDG targets 1.4 and 17.14.

397 **3.2.7 Sustainable agriculture for management of natural resources and heritage**

398 The SI initiatives in this group are aimed at sustainable agriculture through sustainable management of
399 natural resources and restoring or preservation of cultural and natural heritage elements in rural
400 landscapes. They are often social farming and farming cooperatives, or examples of community farming

401 like those in group 4, but with a more specific focus on environmental aspects, such as organic
402 agriculture and environmental conservation.

403 **3.2.8 Sustainable forest management**

404 Group 8 includes 19 SI initiatives aiming to improve forest management, through a diversified offer of
405 services and products. Such initiatives mainly impact SDG 12 (12.2 on sustainable management and
406 efficient use of natural resources) and SDG 15 (15.1 on sustainable use of terrestrial and inland
407 freshwater ecosystems and 15.2 on sustainable management of all types of forests), and to some extent
408 SDG 11 (11.4 on the world's cultural and natural heritage). The initiatives usually target forest owners,
409 through communal forests or cooperatives, although many other stakeholders are involved (policy
410 makers, advisors, research, volunteers, etc.).

411 **3.2.9 Multi-SDG targets initiatives**

412 This final group includes SI initiatives with a broad spectrum, which cover multiple SDG targets. These
413 initiatives are usually structured as large regional or national associations or platforms, which focus on
414 combined agro-forestry-development aspects. They tend to address safeguarding and management of
415 sustainable food production models and natural ecosystems (SDG 15 – Life on land; SDG 2 – Zero
416 hunger), but also focus on larger transversal targets of sustainable development (e.g. target 17.14).

417 **4 Discussion**

418 In this section we firstly discuss the results focusing on the most/least frequent environmental
419 governance fields impacted by the grassroots SI initiatives. We then examine our findings in the light of
420 the current global transition towards a green economy and consider the extent to which SI can
421 contribute to global environmental targets as those highlighted by the SDGs. Finally, we present the
422 limitation of our assessment and some final recommendations.

423 **4.1. Environmental impacts of SI initiatives**

424 Our results indicate that SI initiatives constitute a set of novel governance arrangements that tackle
425 environmental challenges at the local level, promoting new ways of doing things through collective
426 actions and networks, which facilitate greener behavioural models. This finding has been highlighted
427 by other scholars, who showed the importance of the environmental dimension for many SI initiatives
428 (Vercher et al., 2020; Ravazzoli et al., 2019; Pol & Ville, 2009). The three most frequent environmental
429 SDGs identified in our sample (SDG targets 12.2, 2.4, and 2.3) are intertwined with relevant societal
430 needs of rural areas. (i) Fostering sustainable resource management links to key socio-economic needs
431 for the revitalization of rural areas (Yin et al., 2019), as well as new forms of managing natural resources
432 based on collective activities (Pretty, 2003). (ii) Innovative environmental-friendly production models
433 often foster fairer economic markers for empowering vulnerable or disadvantaged groups of society
434 (Tulla et al., 2017). (iii) Equal access to land, directly relates to securing property rights of individuals
435 and poverty alleviation (Oates et al., 2020). All such socio-ecological challenges are of paramount
436 importance for the global policy agenda, as highlighted by e.g. the Rio Declaration on Environment and
437 Development (Agenda 21) adopted in 1992, which called for a tighter inclusion of local communities
438 for local sustainable development (United Nations, 1992). Beside the above-mentioned synergies,
439 trade-offs, can also emerge, as frictions between contrasting goals and targets. Trade-offs can be more
440 prominent in cases where fewer SDGs impacts have been identified counteracting the impacts on other
441 SDGs. We argue that the likelihood that the SI promoters overlooked negative social-economic-
442 environmental interactions at a local level is limited, as this would be detrimental for the SI emergence
443 and establishment, due to the limited number of beneficiaries in rural settings. Additionally, we believe
444 that innovators initiating environmental SI initiatives, tend to seek and establish synergies with certain
445 socio-economic impacts linked to the main context-based issues of the rural area where the initiative

446 operates (e.g., depopulation, lack of services, limited transports, lack of economic opportunities for
447 youth, etc.). If trade-offs do become evident, they should be assessed at a regional or national level, as
448 to measure any aggregated and considerable negative interactions across Goals (Nilsson et al., 2016)

449 From our results we can also see that SI initiatives tend to focus on one to three environmental targets.
450 This suggests that SI initiatives, as locally grounded schemes, are often centred around few specific
451 needs, which a group of actors seek to fulfil through changed social practices (Dalla Torre et al., 2020).
452 Yet, most of the analysed SIs contribute to more than one objective. This could be explained by the fact
453 that people in rural areas often face simultaneously different environmental challenges. Since rural
454 areas are sparsely populated, it is more efficient for SI actors to coordinate local initiatives towards
455 improving collective wellbeing in various directions. This is usually done by either combining
456 environmental impacts with socio-economic outcomes, or by consolidating different environmental
457 targets into one common vision. SI thus appears as a useful instrument for improving coherence across
458 different policy fields (e.g. Nilsson et al, 2012). Our findings also indicate that SIs may enhance bridging
459 social capital by interconnecting local SI initiatives through larger-scale networks (e.g. groups 6 and 7).
460 Besides its potential advocacy role, this networking level facilitates out- and up-scaling², thus
461 supporting transformative and incremental innovations (Biggs et al, 2010). Bridging social capital also
462 fosters adaptability of socio-ecological systems by providing a continuous innovation flows, tackling
463 both societal and environmental challenges (Baker & Mehmood, 2015). We also identified that SI cases
464 characterized by large regional or national associations or platforms (group 9) address more than one
465 SDG environmental target. This can be linked to the fact that they tend to have a policy-coherent vision,
466 since many of the actors in the core group have links to policy development. On the contrary, small,
467 bottom-up, and local initiatives, tend to emerge in relation to specific context-based objectives (e.g.
468 requirement for a recycling scheme) and do not necessarily have immediate synergies with other SDGs.
469 This, however, is not a shortcoming but rather an intrinsic characteristic of many SI models in rural
470 areas, which often evolve and diversify over time forming synergistic relationships with other initiatives
471 to address multiple goals. The role of orchestrating policies become thus extremely relevant promoting
472 policy measures which can support constellation of diverse local SIs to improve their coherence at
473 national level (Slee & Mosdale, 2020).

474 Complementing Eichler and Schwarz (2019), our results prove the relevant contribution of SI to the
475 environmental SDG targets –at least in the analysed rural areas. Yet, we also identified a series of
476 environmental gaps, not covered by the SI catalogue. We related this finding to two main factors: (i)
477 inherent limitation of our sample, which focuses exclusively on rural challenges for European and
478 circum-Mediterranean countries (e.g. SI cases in the marine context are scarce, and where drinkable
479 water or poaching constitute less problematic challenges than in other global regions); and (ii) the local
480 level of most SIs in the sample. This latter point precludes the studied cases to achieve environmental
481 SDG targets which can be tackled only at larger international and institutional level (such as the target
482 12.c on fossil-fuel subsidies rationalisation).

483 Finally, our findings also show that rural development and forestry-based SI initiatives appear to tackle
484 multiple environmental aspects through the same project. This contrasts with SI agricultural initiatives,
485 which tends to be narrower in their scope. This might be related to the fact that rural development
486 initiatives often act at landscape level, and thus involve multiple user-groups and have environmental
487 needs to fulfil (e.g. from natural heritage to recycling). The scope of forestry SI initiatives is instead
488 gradually converging towards forest multifunctionality and ecosystem services approaches; a

² Scale Up: “Changing institutions including policy rules and laws”; Scale Out: replicating and disseminating the model, with “increasing number of people or communities impacted”. (Moore and Riddell, 2015)

489 diversification of the sector that provides opportunities for the current bio-economy transition (Ludvig
490 et al., 2019; Melnykovych et al., 2018).

491 Our study uses the SDG classification to assess the environmental impacts of various SI initiatives,
492 proving to be a useful analytical tool for categorizing environmental impacts of policy relevance at
493 international level. However, this approach has several limitations. First, the catalogue of initiatives is
494 not statistically representative of the population of interest, with probable overrepresentation of
495 specific sectors. This is common in exploratory studies of this nature. Therefore, our results should be
496 read as purely descriptive. Second, when classifying the SI initiatives, we relied heavily on secondary
497 information retrieved through web-searches. However, SIs are often local and do not necessarily have
498 the capabilities of developing fully informative web interfaces. This limited availability of information
499 can affect the overall assessment (e.g. mixing impacts with desired objectives).

500 **4.2. Social Innovations: promising governance mechanisms for a green transition**

501 SI models promote concerted actions that pursue a shared vision —a key element of cognitive social
502 capital, (Nahapiet and Ghoshal, 1998). Cognitive social capital, jointly with shared interpretations and
503 narratives, predisposes people to mutually beneficial collective actions (Górriz-Mifsud et al., 2016). The
504 creation of such shared visions can help in ground-setting new social paradigms leading towards
505 greener societal models. SI can thus instil new development pathways for a place-based environmental
506 governance (Baker & Mehmood; 2015), where environmental changes and social processes are
507 mutually treated acknowledging their intrinsic feedback loops. If the policy framework recognises that
508 systematic changes can only be obtained with synergic top-down (i.e. overarching policy frameworks
509 such as the SDGs; national and EU bioeconomy strategies, the 1992 Convention on Biological Diversity)
510 and bottom-up approaches, (Baker, & Eckerberg, 2008), then SI emerges as a significant tool. SI can
511 support new partnerships that can tackle local needs through the lens of societal challenges in the
512 global Anthropocene (Frantzeskaki & Rok, 2018).

513 In our review we identified how for instance the SIs of groups 4 and 7 contribute to the “*Farm to Fork*
514 *strategy*”, an important pillar of the EU Green Deal, seeking to transform the sustainability of food value
515 chains (European Commission, 2020a). SIs contribute by making agricultural supply chains shorter,
516 ensuring a fair economic return in the supply chain while at the same time improving human well-being
517 by enhancing the social inclusion of marginalized and minority groups. Moreover, innovation cases of
518 group 7 would also contribute to the EU Biodiversity Strategy (European Commission, 2020b), by
519 enhancing the sustainability of agriculture by reducing pesticides and halting biodiversity loss, amongst
520 other practices. Along these lines, Group 8 plays a relevant role for operationalising and modulating
521 on-the-ground national and European Bioeconomy Strategies and the European Forest Strategy. This
522 is done through small-scale viable value chains via participative mechanisms (e.g. forest owners’
523 platforms and associations) and diversifying the services of the forestry sector (Barlagne et al., 2021;
524 Ludvig et al., 2019). Moreover, SIs in marginalized and rural areas may contribute to enhance socio-
525 ecological resilience in landscapes, bridging forest management with rural development activities and
526 thus contributing to reducing land abandonment and natural hazards such as forest fires, and erosion
527 (Rodríguez Fernández-Blanco et al., 2021). Climate change is affecting all sectors in society and the
528 importance of adaptation to its impacts is recognized globally (European Commission 2021). Due to a
529 strong focus on nature-based solutions, disaster risk prevention, and social, environmental and cultural
530 benefits, SIs in all groups can contribute to the EU strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change.

531 The acceleration of global changes is challenging planetary resilience. The EEA (2015) defines these
532 interdependent negative changes as “*global megatrends*”, highlighting their large-scale, high impact
533 and inherent transversality and interdependency across sectors and societies (e.g. urbanization,
534 growing pressure on ecosystems, diverging population trends, etc.). While this global-to-European

535 vision is useful for environmental policy makers, in the recognition of intrinsic relationships between
536 otherwise dissimilar processes (e.g. rural depopulation and increasing wildfire risk; Tedim et al., 2016)
537 so that appropriate funding can be injected through overarching financing schemes (e.g. the European
538 Green Deal aiming at transforming Europe into a “*resource-efficient and competitive economy*” by
539 2050; European Commission, 2020c), the need for actions exists at all scales, above all at local level. SI
540 can provide the proper tool to initiate a new approach favourable to rural development (Slee et al.,
541 2018). Our results showcase that 71% of the 238 SI initiatives assessed, across Europe and circum
542 Mediterranean countries have a variety of positive environmental impacts on local territories. Although
543 such impacts are localized, they can be quantified through targeted assessment tools (i.e. the SIMRA
544 Evaluation manual to assess SI; Secco et al., 2020), as to assimilate them to national quantitative targets
545 or international frameworks such as the SDGs.

546 5 Conclusions

547 The aims of this study were to identify the main environmental impacts of SI initiatives and explore the
548 role of SI in contributing towards a green transition. We can conclude that:

- 549 • Addressing environmental challenges is a common focus within the rural SI initiatives assessed,
550 combined with social, economic, and institutional needs. In particular, we identified nine
551 groups of SI tackling different environmental governance fields.
- 552 • We recognized the functional role of SI as a novel governance mechanism contributing towards
553 achieving the environmental SDGs, thus setting in motion a transition towards a greener world.
554 With a favourable policy framework, SI can play synergistically with top-down legislative
555 frameworks to overcome global climate change and environmental degradation challenges.

556 It is therefore possible to conclude that this study provides a basis to study in a systematic way the
557 contribution of SI to environmental challenges. Further research is needed to expand these results to
558 improve statistical robustness, as well as incorporating in-depth case-study empirical data into the
559 assessment.

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7 Tables

Table 1. 161 Social Innovation Initiatives classified by the number of SDG targets they address as well as their geographical scale, sector, and establishment date. Numbers in bold represent the most abundant categories for each class.

Number of SDG targets		Geographical scale				Sector			Establishment date				
		%	Local	Regional	National	International	Agriculture	Forestry	Rural Development	1971-1980	1981-1990	1991-2000	2001-2010
1-5	69	37%	15%	13%	2%	17%	11%	39%	1%	1%	8%	23%	32%
6-10	23	13%	5%	4%	2%	7%	4%	13%	0%	1%	4%	9%	12%
11-15	6	3%	3%	1%	1%	1%	3%	3%	0%	0%	0%	2%	5%
16-18	2	1%	0%	1%	0%	0%	1%	1%	1%	0%	0%	1%	1%

8 Figure legends

Figure 1. Hierarchical scheme of the impacts of SI. Orange boxes represent the categories considered in this study. Source: own elaboration based on Secco et al. (2017).

Figure 2. Frequency (in number of initiatives) of 65 environmental SDGs targets across a sample of 161 Social Innovation Initiatives. Yellow bars indicate the most frequent targets (above 20%), while red bars indicate the least frequent targets (less than 10%).

Figure 3. Frequency plot of 161 Social Innovation Initiatives classified by the number of different environmental SDG targets they address simultaneously.

Figure 4. Sankey diagram showing the breakdown of the environmental impacts across the 8 groups of SI initiatives by SDGs (Multi-SDG targets initiatives are excluded from the diagram).

9 Appendices

9.1. Appendix 1

List of the selected SDGs with environmental dimension which were used for the assessment of the SI case-studies. The keywords related to the environmental component is highlighted in bold.

1.4 By 2030, ensure that all men and women, in particular the poor and the vulnerable, have equal rights to economic resources, as well as access to basic services, **ownership and control over land** and other forms of property, inheritance, **natural resources**, appropriate new technology and financial services, including microfinance

1.5 By 2030, build the resilience of the poor and those in vulnerable situations and reduce their **exposure and vulnerability to climate-related extreme events** and other economic, social and **environmental shocks and disasters**

2.3 By 2030, **double the agricultural productivity** and incomes of small-scale food producers, in particular women, indigenous peoples, family farmers, pastoralists and fishers, including through secure and equal access to land, other productive resources and inputs, knowledge, financial services, markets and opportunities for value addition and non-farm employment

2.4 By 2030, ensure **sustainable food production systems** and implement **resilient agricultural practices** that increase productivity and production, that help maintain ecosystems, that strengthen capacity for adaptation to climate change, extreme weather, drought, flooding and other disasters and that progressively improve land and soil quality

2.5 By 2020, maintain the **genetic diversity of seeds, cultivated plants and farmed and domesticated animals and their related wild species**, including through soundly managed and diversified seed and plant banks at the national, regional and international levels, and promote access to and fair and equitable sharing of benefits arising from the utilization of genetic resources and associated traditional knowledge, as internationally agreed

3.9 By 2030, substantially reduce the number of deaths and illnesses from **hazardous chemicals and air, water and soil pollution and contamination**

6.1 By 2030, achieve universal and equitable **access to safe and affordable drinking water** for all

6.3 By 2030, improve **water quality** by reducing pollution, eliminating dumping and minimizing release of hazardous chemicals and materials, halving the proportion of untreated wastewater and substantially increasing recycling and safe reuse globally

6.4 By 2030, substantially increase **water-use efficiency** across all sectors and ensure sustainable withdrawals and supply of freshwater to address water scarcity and substantially reduce the number of people suffering from water scarcity

6.5 By 2030, implement **integrated water resources management** at all levels, including through transboundary cooperation as appropriate

6.6 By 2020, protect and restore **water-related ecosystems**, including mountains, forests, wetlands, rivers, aquifers and lakes

6.b Support and strengthen the participation of local communities in improving **water and sanitation management**

7.1 By 2030, ensure universal access to affordable, reliable and modern **energy services**

7.2 By 2030, increase substantially the **share of renewable energy** in the global energy mix

7.3 By 2030, double the global rate of improvement in **energy efficiency**

7.a By 2030, enhance international cooperation to facilitate access to **clean energy research and technology**, including renewable energy, energy efficiency and advanced and cleaner fossil-fuel technology, and promote investment in energy infrastructure and clean energy technology

8.4 Improve progressively, through 2030, **global resource efficiency in consumption and production** and endeavour to decouple economic growth from environmental degradation, in accordance with the 10 Year Framework of Programmes on Sustainable Consumption and Production, with developed countries taking the lead

8.9 By 2030, devise and implement policies to promote **sustainable tourism** that creates jobs and promotes local culture and products

9.1 Develop **quality, reliable, sustainable and resilient infrastructure**, including regional and transborder infrastructure, to support economic development and human well-being, with a focus on affordable and equitable access for all

9.4 By 2030, upgrade infrastructure and retrofit **industries** to make them **sustainable**, with increased resource-use efficiency and greater adoption of clean and environmentally sound technologies and industrial processes, with all countries taking action in accordance with their respective capabilities

11.2 By 2030, provide access to safe, affordable, accessible and **sustainable transport systems** for all, improving road safety, notably by expanding public transport, with special attention to the needs of those in vulnerable situations, women, children, persons with disabilities and older persons

11.3 By 2030, enhance inclusive and **sustainable urbanization** and capacity for participatory, integrated and sustainable human settlement planning and management in all countries

11.4 Strengthen efforts to protect and safeguard the **world's** cultural and **natural heritage**

11.5 By 2030, significantly reduce the number of deaths and the number of people affected and substantially decrease the direct economic losses relative to global gross domestic product caused by **disasters**, including water-related disasters, with a focus on protecting the poor and people in vulnerable situations

11.6 By 2030, reduce the adverse per capita **environmental impact of cities**, including by paying special attention to air quality and municipal and other waste management

11.7 By 2030, provide universal access to safe, inclusive and accessible, **green and public spaces**, in particular for women and children, older persons and persons with disabilities

11.a Support positive economic, social and environmental **links between urban, peri-urban and rural areas** by strengthening national and regional development planning

11.b By 2020, substantially increase the number of **cities and human settlements** adopting and implementing integrated policies and plans towards inclusion, **resource efficiency, mitigation and adaptation to climate change, resilience to disasters**, and develop and implement, in line with the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015–2030, holistic disaster risk management at all levels

12.2 By 2030, achieve the **sustainable management and efficient use of natural resources**

12.3 By 2030, halve per capita global **food waste** at the retail and consumer levels and reduce **food losses** along production and supply chains, including post-harvest losses

12.4 By 2020, achieve the **environmentally sound management of chemicals and all wastes** throughout their life cycle, in accordance with agreed international frameworks, and significantly reduce their release to air, water and soil in order to minimize their adverse impacts on human health and the environment

12.5 By 2030, substantially **reduce waste generation** through prevention, reduction, recycling and reuse

12.6 Encourage **companies**, especially large and transnational companies, to adopt **sustainable practices** and to integrate sustainability information into their reporting cycle

12.7 Promote **public procurement** practices that are **sustainable**, in accordance with national policies and priorities

12.8 By 2030, ensure that people everywhere have the relevant information and **awareness for sustainable development** and lifestyles in harmony with nature

12.b Develop and implement tools to monitor sustainable development impacts for **sustainable tourism** that creates jobs and promotes local culture and products

12.c **Rationalize** inefficient **fossil-fuel subsidies** that encourage wasteful consumption by removing market distortions, in accordance with national circumstances, including by restructuring taxation and phasing out those harmful subsidies, where they exist, to reflect their environmental impacts, taking fully into account the specific needs and conditions of developing countries and minimizing the possible adverse impacts on their development in a manner that protects the poor and the affected communities

13.1 Strengthen **resilience and adaptive capacity to climate-related hazards and natural disasters** in all countries

13.2 Integrate **climate change measures** into national policies, strategies and planning

13.3 Improve education, **awareness-raising** and human and institutional capacity on climate change mitigation, adaptation, impact reduction and early warning

13.a Implement the commitment undertaken by developed-country parties to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change to a goal of mobilizing jointly \$100 billion annually by 2020 from all sources to address the needs of developing countries in the context of meaningful mitigation actions and transparency on implementation and fully operationalize the **Green Climate Fund** through its capitalization as soon as possible

13.b Promote mechanisms for raising capacity for effective **climate change-related planning and management** in least developed countries and small island developing States, including focusing on women, youth and local and marginalized communities

14.1 By 2025, prevent and significantly **reduce marine pollution** of all kinds, in particular from land-based activities, including marine debris and nutrient pollution

14.2 By 2020, sustainably **manage and protect marine and coastal ecosystems** to avoid significant adverse impacts, including by strengthening their resilience, and take action for their restoration in order to achieve healthy and productive oceans

14.3 Minimize and address the impacts of **ocean acidification**, including through enhanced scientific cooperation at all levels

14.4 By 2020, effectively regulate harvesting and end **overfishing, illegal, unreported and unregulated fishing and destructive fishing practices** and implement science-based management plans, in order to restore fish stocks in the shortest time feasible, at least to levels that can produce maximum sustainable yield as determined by their biological characteristics

14.5 By 2020, conserve at least 10 per cent of **coastal and marine areas**, consistent with national and international law and based on the best available scientific information

14.6 By 2020, prohibit certain forms of **fisheries subsidies** which contribute to overcapacity and overfishing, eliminate subsidies that contribute to illegal, unreported and unregulated fishing and refrain from introducing new such subsidies, recognizing that appropriate and effective special and differential treatment for developing and least developed countries should be an integral part of the World Trade Organization fisheries subsidies negotiation³

14.7 By 2030, increase the economic benefits to small island developing States and least developed countries from the **sustainable use of marine resources**, including through sustainable management of fisheries, aquaculture and tourism

14.a Increase scientific knowledge, develop research capacity and transfer **marine technology**, taking into account the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission Criteria and Guidelines on the Transfer of Marine Technology, in order to improve ocean health and to enhance the contribution of marine biodiversity to the development of developing countries, in particular small island developing States and least developed countries

14.b Provide access for **small-scale artisanal fishers** to marine resources and markets

14.c Enhance the conservation and **sustainable use of oceans** and their resources by implementing international law as reflected in the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea, which provides the legal framework for the conservation and sustainable use of oceans and their resources, as recalled in paragraph 158 of “The future we want”

15.1 By 2020, ensure the conservation, restoration and **sustainable use of terrestrial and inland freshwater ecosystems** and their services, in particular forests, wetlands, mountains and drylands, in line with obligations under international agreements

15.2 By 2020, promote the implementation of **sustainable management of all types of forests**, halt deforestation, restore degraded forests and substantially increase afforestation and reforestation globally

15.3 By 2030, **combat desertification**, restore degraded land and soil, including land affected by desertification, drought and floods, and strive to achieve a land degradation-neutral world

15.4 By 2030, ensure the **conservation of mountain ecosystems**, including their biodiversity, in order to enhance their capacity to provide benefits that are essential for sustainable development

15.5 Take urgent and significant action to **reduce the degradation of natural habitats**, halt the loss of biodiversity and, by 2020, protect and prevent the extinction of threatened species

15.6 Promote fair and equitable sharing of the benefits arising from the **utilization of genetic resources** and promote appropriate access to such resources, as internationally agreed

15.7 Take urgent action to **end poaching and trafficking of protected species** of flora and fauna and address both demand and supply of illegal wildlife products

15.8 By 2020, introduce measures to prevent the introduction and significantly reduce the impact of **invasive alien species** on land and water ecosystems and control or eradicate the priority species

15.9 By 2020, integrate **ecosystem and biodiversity values** into national and local planning, development processes, poverty reduction strategies and accounts

15.a Mobilize and significantly increase financial resources from all sources to **conserve and sustainably use biodiversity and ecosystems**

15.b Mobilize significant resources from all sources and at all levels to finance **sustainable forest management** and provide adequate incentives to developing countries to advance such management, including for conservation and reforestation

15.c Enhance global support for efforts to **combat poaching and trafficking of protected species**, including by increasing the capacity of local communities to pursue sustainable livelihood opportunities

17.14 Enhance **policy coherence for sustainable development**

9.2. Appendix 2

Dendrogram of 170 SI initiatives classified according to 65 environmental SDG targets. A height of 1.5 (dotted line) was selected to partition the sample into 9 groups (indicated by the black numbers), with similar environmental patterns. After inspecting the dendrogram results, nine initiatives were identified as wrongly assessed and thus removed from the sample, bringing the final dataset to 161 observations.

9.3. Appendix 3

Additional description of the 9 identified SI groups with examples from the SIMRA SI catalogue. The SI initiatives are indicated with their corresponding name as they appear in the SIMRA catalogue of cases in italics, followed by the location (Alpha-2 country code), if not reported in the SI name. INT indicates that the SI initiative operates at an international level.

1. Increasing awareness for environmental protection

Initiatives in this group target children and young individuals (e.g. outdoor schools for children: *Educare all'aria aperta*, IT), while others target vulnerable groups (e.g. prisoners from juvenile prisons, students dropping out of school and children with disabilities: *Tășuleasa Social association*; RO). Three types of SI initiatives can be identified in this group: (i) initiatives organized into structured educational programs (e.g. nature schools), (ii) awareness-raising initiatives aiming at providing to beneficiaries an overview of existing and yet forgotten traditional practices for enhancing the preservation of natural and cultural heritage at landscape level (e.g. alpine farming: *Team Karwendel*, AT; restoration and renovation of traditional buildings: *Recartografia*, ES; traditional shepherding: *Escola de pastors*, ES), (iii) awareness-raising initiatives aimed at fostering responsible consumption and production practices (e.g. organic farming and fair trade: *Gwad' Amap - Dot Soley*, FR). In some specific cases, these initiatives have been organized to protest against large industrial scale projects (*Noidanlukko*, FI), or can take the format of co-working space for peri-urban knowledge exchange (*Rural HUB*, RS). Overall, the initiatives within this group strongly rely on volunteers.

2. Sustainable tourism for natural protection and coherent policy development

Some of the Group 2 initiatives focus on promoting new means of travel (e.g. hiking or biking trails e.g. *Hiking Routes in Balaton Uplands*, HU; *Mezőcsát*, HU). Others developed new integrated approaches to tourism which can enhance cooperation between public and private actors (*Italy Heartland*, IT; or the scattered hotel model developed in *Vrbanj*, HR) to increase local or regional coherence towards sustainable development. Finally, some initiatives integrate sustainable tourism practices (e.g. hikes) with local history and tradition and cultural heritage to boost the socio-economy of local communities (*Nallihan Tourism Volunteers Association*, TR; Masar Ibrahim Al-Khalil; PS).

3. Sustainable and renewable energy

Twelve energy related initiatives are included in this group, focusing on either supply of energy through direct installations (e.g. *Udny Community Trust Community Wind Turbine*, UK) or through mechanisms allowing access to renewable energy, like cooperatives (e.g. *Som Energia*, ES), land ownership (e.g. *North West Mull Community Woodland Company*, UK), third sector local development agencies (e.g. *Huntly Development Trust*, UK). All energy sources were renewable (SDG 7 – Affordable and clean energy) and nature-based with installations based on the following sources: (i) water/hydroelectric, (ii) forest biomass, (iii) wind, and (iv) mixed renewable sources (e.g. *Local green energy initiatives in The Netherlands*). Seven cooperative-focused SI showed clear links to renewable energy (SDG 7) regardless of the source, however with clear place-based motivations such as bringing energy to remote places such as UK islands (e.g. “*ACCESS: Assisting Communities to Connect to Electric Sustainable Sources*”, UK; wind turbine installation on the Isle of Mull) and buffering shortages (due to e.g. insufficient infrastructure, peaks in demand, need for energy independence due to available natural resources, e.g. *Bio-energy production by farmers*, AT). Indirect goals aim at reducing energy poverty and fossil fuel dependence. Policy adherence mechanisms or network development were only evident in a minority of cases (SDG target 17.14), and in one case the SI initiated to replace a policy failure. Sustainable use

of resources (SDG 11) were linked to landscape approaches that included cultural heritage (SDG target 12.2).

4. Sustainable food production models in agriculture

The SI initiatives in group 4 can be approximately divided in two types (i) social farming initiatives aimed at integrating people with a risk of social exclusion such as disabled people (*Agricoltura Capodarco Società Cooperativa Sociale*, IT), prisoners (*Gorgona Agricultural Penal Colony*, IT), and groups of different gender, age, ethnic or religious background (*Riuverd*, ES; *Adelwöhrerhof*, AT), and (ii) cooperatives aimed at improving cooperation in rural communities in organising agricultural supply chains. Very often these include community farming initiatives (*Gela Ochsenherz*, AT) short supply chains (*Del Monte de Tabuyo*, ES) and/or initiatives promoting contact between primary producers and local/urban consumers (*HAWARU Hof-Solidarische Landwirtschaft*, AT; *Fruit Tree adoption Tarlamvar*, TR).

5. Waste reduction and recycling

For some initiatives such as the *Call of the Earth community recycling scheme* (LB), the primary objective was to implement a system of recycling where no such service existed. The *CAUTO social cooperative* (IT) works with supermarkets to reduce waste by redistributing unsold food for human or animal nutrition. In some cases, recycling is one component of broader participatory community development projects such as the *Lika womens' social cooperative* (HR) where participants create products from recycled materials. Other initiatives provide indirect environmental benefit – e.g. *VISP* (AT) offers unemployed people the opportunity to reintegrate into the labour market through partnerships between social enterprise and the waste management sector where participants can be trained in new skills that have an environmental benefit. The remaining schemes relate to sustainable mobility e.g. *Zdrav Šolar* (SI) provides more sustainable school transport options for children i.e. walking and cycling routes and *TALENTE mobil* (AT) promotes pooling of private transportation reducing car use.

6. Hubs and partnerships to improve territorial development

This group compiles very heterogeneous initiatives, which range from local co-ops and social farms, to landscape (*French forest territorial charters*) and national-level approaches (the Austrian *Green Care*, or the Moroccan *Participatory agrolabel*). These initiatives contain a relevant coordination component as they are either networks or umbrella platforms (e.g. *Forum Nazionale d'Agricoltura Sociale*, IT, or the *Rural Development Network of Montenegro*), or represent a coalition between different agents (public and private actors – e.g. *dairy producer co-ops*, TN; or farmers with agrofood companies –e.g. the *Skylark Foundation*, NL). These SIs reflect alliances between actors of different sectors with a wider rural developmental vision than in the other groups (more sectorial-specific), contributing mainly to the SDG targets 1.4 and 17.14. Some of these initiatives directly manage natural resources as primary production, relying on the potential of nature-based activities as therapy/empowerment, inclusion, and livelihood source. Some of these networks aim at facilitating agroecology through alternative certification systems –e.g. *Participatory Guarantee System* (INT)- that are more accessible to farmers than mainstream third-party labels. This group then contributes less frequently to SDG targets 2.3 and 2.4. The economic component is a commonality across the initiatives in this group - i.e. selling products makes the initiative economically viable or the initiative reduces household expenditures (e.g. *Näh and Reparatur Café*, AT), which is intertwined with other welfare objectives -e.g. improved women economic independence in the Lebanese co-op *Jana Al-Ayadi*, mental care in the Czech *Freedom Farm in the Confluence*, reduction of discrimination in the Serbian *Optimist association*, compatibility of forest uses in the French territorial charters, refugee integration in the Italian *Rise Hub*, or strengthened rural employment in the Swiss *Reseau de Fleurons*.

7. Sustainable agriculture for management of natural resources and heritage

Many of the initiatives aim to restore degraded landscapes (*Mazi farm*, GR) recover abandoned agricultural areas (*Adotta un terrazzamento*, IT), enhance (agro-)biodiversity in degraded landscapes (*Acacias for all*, TN) and restore cultural or natural heritage elements in the landscapes (*TERRAVIVA*, IT). Some of the cases also try to enhance rural tourism (*Apadrina un Olivo*, ES), and very often this goes hand in hand with initiatives that are restoring cultural or natural heritage sites or promoting local and traditional food (*ASAT partnerships*, RO). The SI initiatives in this group 7 differ from group 4 as these address additionally targets 11.4 (strengthen efforts to protect and safeguard the world's cultural and natural heritage) and 12.2 (sustainable management and efficient use of natural resources). This group also includes cases of networks (*Terra Madre*, IT), online platforms (*Good4Trust*, TR; *Apiform beekeeping*, BA) and crowd funding initiatives (*Blue bees*, FR) that share similar aims, i.e. improving the environmental farming sustainability, promoting biodiversity, connecting responsible producers, or restoring rural cultural and natural heritage elements.

8. Sustainable forest management

The SIs of this group include six main types of initiatives: (i) restoration of abandoned forests or ancient practices e.g. charcoal burning, enhancing the preservation of natural and cultural heritage (*Llais y Goedwig*, UK; *Montes de Socios*, ES; *Oglarska deželca*, SI), (ii) knowledge sharing and capacity building on skills to empower the community (e.g. unemployed youth or other vulnerable groups) and its wellbeing (*S4RE*, XK), (iii) valorisation and diversification of Non-Wood Forest Product (berries, mushrooms, medicinal plants, cork, laurel; *ARDAC*, LB), payment for ecosystem services and tourism, enhancing the economy through new value chains and microenterprises (*ADM market development*, TN; *Laggan Forest Trust*, UK; ; *LAMO*, IT; *S4RE*, XK), (iv) improving the resilience of forests to disturbances (winds, pests, fires) through communication to practitioners (*Associació de Gestors Forestals de les Gavarres*, ES) or Climate-Smart Forestry practices (*Carbon smart forestry in self-organized forest commons regime*, SK; *ENERBOSC*, ES), v) education through forest schools (*Abriachan Forest Trust*, UK), and (vi) digitalization of forest management (*My forest mobile cooperative*, SI).

9. Multi-SDG targets initiatives

Examples of this group include: (i) landscape-based platforms for setting up participatory and voluntary agreements for managing natural resources (*Improving Lebanese forests areas' governance through the implementation of participatory approaches*; *Land Stewardship Networks*, ES; *Plataforma Forestal Valenciana*, ES), (ii) transnational cooperation projects for knowledge sharing (*Lebensqualität durch Nähe*, INT; *Inclufar*, INT).